

Status and prospects of selected global freight forwarding & logistics companies in Parañaque City towards an improved logistics service quality

Jenny A. Cipriano*, Romeo I. Parceró

Master of Business Administration, Graduate Studies Department, St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor City, Cavite, Philippines

Abstract

The importance of logistics service quality (LSQ) is rising. The quantity of studies on the quality of logistics services has increased recently. The study looked at how consumers and workers of global freight-forwarding and logistics organizations felt about logistics service quality (LSQ) based on their demographic profile. The study employed a descriptive survey approach using a questionnaire. Respondents of the study are the one hundred five (105) customers of global freight-forwarding companies in Paranaque City and one hundred forty-eight (148) employees of the global freight-forwarding companies were the subjects of the study. Saturation sampling was conducted to poll the full population of freight forwarding and logistics service providers. Results showed that age, gender, and job level of the employees of global freight-forwarding companies is not statistically significant on the seven (7) factors of logistics service quality. The findings also implied that information quality is the least priority among the factors as perceived by the employees of global freight-forwarding companies. An improved logistics service quality in freight forwarding business in Paranaque can be achieved by investing to differentials/competitive advantage, specifically to Personnel Contact Quality. This article can serve as a guide for quality management methods in the freight and forwarding business and serves as the foundation for additional research for empirical studies.

Keywords: Logistics service quality; global freight forwarding; logistics

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Introduction

In their study, Arabelen and Kaya (2021) reaffirmed how the expectations of Logistics Services Providers (LSPs) and the influence that globalization and complex supply chain networks have had on service delivery. The importance of logistics service quality (LSQ) to LSPs and users of logistics services is growing. The quantity of studies on the quality of logistics services has increased recently. In an effort to create a measurement model that may be employed to assess logistics services as a whole, researchers have been attempting to determine what makes logistics services quality (LSQ) tick. Nonetheless, scholars are constantly debating the different methods because there is currently no standard or accepted LSQ measuring model in the literature. With a systematic approach and systematic process, this study looks at previous research findings to determine what LSQ measuring dimensions to recommend.

In the aforementioned study, Arabelen and Kaya (2021) employed exact keyword and keyword cluster searches as part of a systematic literature analysis to search academic databases for related papers published within a certain time window. The study patterns and methodologies on logistics service quality that are most frequently employed have been identified, as well as the most often used LSQ dimensions and variables. In addition, the most commonly utilized service quality methodologies and measurement models were described. The findings of a comprehensive literature study have been compiled, and dimensions have been determined (Thai, 2013).

Due to the high demand for freight forwarding and logistics because of the pandemic. Medical supplies and other essential materials to fight the virus are needed to transport globally. Because of the variety of stochastic factors that influence demand and the scarcity of information on demand characteristics, estimating demand for forwarding services is especially difficult. On the basis of data gathered from Internet logistics portals, the author develops a method for estimating demand parameters for forwarding services. A demand model for forwarding services was constructed based on the estimated parameters, as well as software to implement it. Demand simulations utilizing the created software show that the model's demand parameters and key empirical data are highly convergent (Naumov, 2018).

Gaudenzi et al.'s (2020) goal on their study is to look at logistics service quality (LSQ) from the standpoint of supply chain quality. A qualitative comparative analysis technique is used to analyze data acquired through a survey of a sample of Italian food firms. The study looks at multiple strategies to achieve customer satisfaction by combining LSQ dimensions rather than using a "single recipe," as most symmetrical techniques do. The study explains how seven LSQ dimensions contribute to high customer satisfaction via various configurations, highlighting and explaining how the various LSQ structures lead to high customer satisfaction through various configurations. This method is unusual in that it uses a configurational approach to find not simply linear correlations between variables, as typical statistical approaches do.

Uvet (2020) research on logistics service quality, set out to learn more about how logistics services influence customers satisfaction. A research was conducted to determine the logistical effectiveness. Factors affecting service quality include employee contact and order placement. condition, punctuality, handling of order discrepancies, and in logistics services, operational information exchange is important. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and structural equation modeling are two methods for analyzing data. This work employed simulation modeling (SEM) to investigate using the five logistical structures to increase customer satisfaction service excellence. Within the area of logistic service quality, these study can be used to explain and increase satisfaction.

The challenges experienced in the COVID-19 pandemic have unleashed a wave of feverish activity in the logistics arena to improve its quality of service. The pandemic disturbs the supply chains in different scenarios. It also serves as a vital tool to analyze the problems and design desirable opportunities to improve the quality of service provided for the customers. In many cases, raising customer satisfaction ratings is not as crucial as improving service quality because of how customers interpret their experiences. Customers' evaluation of the overall excellence of the service was characterized as perceived service quality. Good service quality increases client happiness, which boosts a company's ability to compete in the market. High service quality can be achieved by identifying service concerns and creating measurements for service performances, outcomes, and customer satisfaction (Johnson & Karlay, 2018).

Generally, businesses are focused on enhancing customer satisfaction by redefining their standards and strategies to face the changing market and challenges, especially in the service sector. Assessing customers' satisfaction level plays a vital role in identifying the customer perception of a given company's services and helps to take appropriate action to retain the customer's satisfaction at the highest level. Thus, successful implementation of a customer focus strategy would require the relevant organization to improve its production (Cai, 2009).

The service sector in our country has been one of the strongest and fast-growing sectors that contributes a big part to the economy. The Philippines' freight forwarding, and logistics industry is a key GDP contributor (Consultancy.asia, 2020). Thus, during the past five years, the vital economy of the nation has expanded. Between 2015 and 2019, the GDP expanded at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of more than 8.5%, while the growth of transportation and storage alone was more than 7.5%.

In addition, the freight forwarding and logistics industry in the country is highly fragmented with domestic and international players. Thus, logistics service quality is the foundation of these businesses that determine customers' satisfaction and competitive edge over competitors. Furthermore, most freight forwarding, and logistics service customers are primarily engaged in manufacturing, export trading, logistics and warehousing services, as well as information and technology (IT). These companies are generally located in the Philippine Economic Zone Authority (PEZA).

In every industry, competition is getting stronger daily, especially in the freight forwarding and logistics industry. Therefore, to maintain the competitive advantage of freight forwarding and logistics service providers, they should be mindful of their customers' perceived service quality. Hence, service quality must meet the customers' expectations and satisfaction by assessing logistics service quality factors and improving them if necessary.

Logistics during the COVID-19 Pandemic

Logistical challenges arise as part of emergency management during the COVID-19 pandemic, which includes risk assessment, preparation, emergency response, and post-event recovery (Yu et al., 2020). Liu et al. (2020) created a logistics network model in the emergency situation, known as SEIR (Susceptible Exposed Infected Recovered), to address an unforeseen pandemic. This model can be used as a tool for decision-making to enhance logistical efficiency in the pandemic by accounting for higher emergency operating expenses and customer demand satisfaction. According to Yu et al. (2020), the logistics network architecture for a pandemic is planned for a relatively short period of time—a few weeks up to several months. In this sense, the government plays a crucial role since it needs to offer a logistical policy as a remedy for the COVID-19 pandemic that is currently raging. The government has created a supply chain "green subsidy" scheme, as it has in the past. In relation to the COVID-19 epidemic, the government must also provide policy logistics (Choi, 2020). An efficient method of delivery of goods is necessary during the COVID-19 pandemic because it can support social distancing efforts to stop the virus from spreading (Singh et al., 2021). A number of locations have been placed under lockdown due to COVID-19. Transportation limitations, a labor shortage, and red zone regulations make certain places unavailable, which causes disruptions in logistics. Accordingly, it is essential to assess warehouse routes and logistics (Singh et al., 2021, as cited in Restuputri et al., 2021).

In addition to employing previously developed models and attempting to validate the quality assessment models, there is a rise in empirical research concerning the Logistics Service Quality (LSQ). There is a rise in empirical investigations on the LSQ subject. Furthermore, several scholars have investigated the link between the LSQ and other characteristics like as loyalty and satisfaction. As a result, the rise in validation studies might be a response to non-conformity in the search field and in the hunt for a study and a generalized LSQ measurement model. Moreover, the majority of researchers choose to create an LSQ model and use quantitative methods to verify its reliability over time, with few qualitative LSQ dimension development studies being conducted. An LSQ model will continuously assess reliability using quantitative techniques (Arabelen & Kaya, 2021).

In relation to the logistics service quality variables, the theoretical framework for this study was adopted from Le et al. (2020). Three elements make up Cat Lai Port's port logistics service model: port personnel, the port logistics service delivery system, and clients. Between those components, information flows based on both hard and soft platforms. The physical infrastructure, machinery, and equipment used to handle shipments at ports make up the hard platform, while the information system for port logistics management is the soft platform (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Port logistics service delivery canvas (Le et al., 2020).

Regarding hard platforms, the port has made investments in a fleet of truck tractors and semi-trailers to relieve internal traffic jams as well as a state-of-the-art method to increase container handling productivity (ship-to-shore crane). The service flow that uses the tangible and intangible platforms of the SDS to connect port employees with consumers is depicted by the red arrows. The blue arrows, on the other hand, show the information and financial transfers from clients to port employees. Customers' and port employees' interacting environment is shaped by both tangible and intangible platforms. Customers connect with those components and thereby experience happiness when they use port logistics services.

To assess service quality and gauge client satisfaction with logistics services, the author suggested a study technique based on the SERVQUAL paradigm (Le et al., 2020). It has been confirmed that the SERVQUAL model's five components have an impact on the quality of port logistics services. In particular, the most essential aspects affecting the quality are assurance, tangibles, and empathy, as well as responsiveness and reliability. This indicates that while utilizing port logistics services, customers are primarily concerned with the port's strong commitment, which is demonstrated by the professionalism of the staff in addressing their concerns, especially those related to the security of their shipments, prompt clearance, and timely delivery or receipt of consignments. Furthermore, the legitimate impact of tangibles highlights the contributions that infrastructure and technology make to raising service standards, which in turn raise customer happiness.

Figure 2. Logistics Service Quality Model (Le et al., 2020)

Statement of the Problem

The study aimed to assess the logistics service quality (LSQ) of the logistics providers' as perceived by the customers and employees of global freight-forwarding companies. This will reveal the factors of logistics service quality as basis for customer satisfaction, status and prospects of selected global freight-forwarding companies in Paranaque City. Specifically, it answers the following questions:

1. What is the perception to logistics service quality of global freight-forwarding and logistics companies' customers and employees according to their demographic profile?
 - 1.1. Customer
 - 1.1.1. Business Type
 - 1.1.2. Civil Status
 - 1.1.3. Job Level
 - 1.1.4. Length of Service
 - 1.2. Employees
 - 1.2.1. Age
 - 1.2.2. Gender
 - 1.2.3. Job Level
2. What is the assessment of the respondents with regards to the factors of logistics service quality:
 - 2.1. Personnel Contact Quality
 - 2.2. Information Quality
 - 2.3. Order Handling Quality
 - 2.4. Physical Distribution Service Quality (PDSQ)
 - 2.5. Timeliness
 - 2.6. Image; and
 - 2.7. Social Responsibility?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profile and factors of logistics service quality?

Hypothesis

The study is premised on the following hypothesis:

H1 – There is no significant difference between demographic profiles of the respondents and their perceived assessment of the factors of logistics service quality.

H2 – There is a significant difference between demographic profiles of the respondents and their perceived assessment of the factors of logistics service quality.

Methodology

A study using descriptive research aims to accurately portray the participants. The main goal of descriptive research is to characterize the study participants (Robinson et al., 2019). The descriptive survey method was employed by the researcher. Its purpose is to collect data regarding the current state of affairs. It entails obtaining, evaluating, categorizing, and tabulating information regarding cause-and-effect relationships in order to create appropriate and precise statistical procedures.

The study employed the descriptive survey approach, which involves employing a questionnaire to collect data on the phenomena's current state and characterize "what exists" in terms of variables or circumstances in a given scenario. The study focused on the customers' perceived logistics service quality. It utilized a questionnaire with the respondents only to be observed in one setting in terms of their responses to the questionnaire.

Participants and Sampling Techniques

Respondents of the study are the one hundred five (105) customers of global freight-forwarding companies in Parañaque City and one hundred forty-eight (148) employees of the global freight-forwarding companies were the subjects of the study. The researcher utilized convenience sampling method for the customers (as respondents). Convenience sampling involves collecting market research data from a sample of respondents who are easily available. Because it is so rapid, easy to use, and reasonably priced, it is the most often utilized sample procedure. It is usually easy to get in touch with members to ask them to join the sample.

On the other hand, since the population employees of the global freight-forwarding companies is lower, this study did not set a sampling limitation for the respondents (employees of the global freight-forwarding companies) and did try to use the entire population of the freight forwarding and logistics service providers as survey samples. This is called saturation sampling. To maximize response rate, the researcher used her connection since the researcher was connected to a freight forwarding and logistics company.

Research Instruments

Questionnaire was prepared and formulated. There are two parts: The first part contains the profile of the respondents, while the second part is the assessment of the logistics quality service. The researcher prepared guide questions that enabled the respondents to answer with regard to how they can assess logistics quality service. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic restrictions, distribution of questionnaires was done through Google Forms.

The instrument was presented to the managers of selected freight forwarding and logistics companies in coming up with a good questionnaire. It was administered to selected managers of selected freight forwarding and logistics companies for pilot test and final revision. Pre-testing served to validate the survey's questionnaire. Finding unclear elements in the instrument was the aim of the pre-test. In light of their feedback, the questionnaire was further improved. Cronbach's Alpha for the reliability data was 0.927, indicating that the tool passed the reliability test.

Data Collection

The preparation and the actual gathering of data were done following certain procedures. After finalizing the instrument, a written request was secured by the researcher from the Dean of the Graduate School of Business Administration. The researcher distributed the questionnaires via electronic mail and phone calls to the respondents with the permission. Items in the questionnaire were explained to the respondents.

Data Analysis Procedure

The completed questionnaires were gathered, meticulously organized and categorized. To achieve the study's goals, the collected data were totaled, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted using weighted mean,

percentage distribution, frequency, and analysis of variance. For easier to understand presentation, the majority of the results were given as tables. The analyses were derived from the responses.

Results and Discussion

Customers of the Global Freight-Forwarding Companies

Table 1 shows perception of customers in terms of level of importance according to business type. The seven (7) LSQ factors are strongly important to business process outsourcing (BPO) and E-commerce industries, followed by trading, and moderately important for manufacturing, freight forwarding, and logistics. While in the engineering sector, personnel contact quality is moderately important, and the other factors were equally slightly important.

Table 1. Perception of the customers of global freight-forwarding companies according to business type

Variables	PCQ	IQ	OHQ	PDSQ	Timeliness	Image	SR
BPO	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
E-commerce	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Trading	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Manufacturing	3	3	3	3	3	3	2
Freight Forwarding & Logistics	3	3	3	3	3	2	3
Engineering	3	2	2	2	2	2	2

Legend: PCQ – Personnel Contact Quality; IQ – Information Quality; OHQ – Order Handling Quality; PDSQ – Physical Distribution Service Quality; SR – Social Responsibility; 5 – Strongly Important; 4 – Important; 3 – Moderately Important; 2 – Slightly Important; 1 – Not Important

Table 2 shows perception of customers in terms of level of importance according to job level. The seven (7) LSQ factors are moderately important in the top management. For those in middle management, information quality, order handling quality, physical distribution service quality, timeliness, and social responsibility are important, whereas personnel contact quality and image are moderately important. Then for supervisory level, only PDSQ is moderately important and the rest LSQ factors are slightly important. While for the rank and file, all LSQ factors are moderately important except from image which was interpreted as important.

Table 2. Perception of the customers of global freight-forwarding companies according to job level

Variables	PCQ	IQ	OHQ	PDSQ	Timeliness	Image	SR
Top Management	3	3	3	3	3	3	2
Middle Management	3	4	4	4	4	3	4
Supervisory	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Rank and File	3	3	3	3	3	2	3

Legend: PCQ – Personnel Contact Quality; IQ – Information Quality; OHQ – Order Handling Quality; PDSQ – Physical Distribution Service Quality; SR – Social Responsibility; 5 – Strongly Important; 4 – Important; 3 – Moderately Important; 2 – Slightly Important; 1 – Not Important

Table 3 shows perception of customers in terms of level of importance according to length of service. Customers with more than five years in their company finds personnel contact quality as moderately important and the other LSQ factors as important. Then, those who have three to five years in service find all LSQ factors are moderately important. Lastly, those with one to three years of service considered all LSQ factors as moderately important except from image quality as important.

Table 3. Perception of the customers of global freight-forwarding companies according to length of service

Variables	PCQ	IQ	OHQ	PDSQ	Timeliness	Image	SR
More than 5 years	3	2	2	2	2	2	2
3-5 years	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
1-3 years	3	3	3	3	3	2	3

Legend: PCQ – Personnel Contact Quality; IQ – Information Quality; OHQ – Order Handling Quality; PDSQ – Physical Distribution Service Quality; SR – Social Responsibility; 5 – Strongly Important; 4 – Important; 3 – Moderately Important; 2 – Slightly Important; 1 – Not Important

Employees of the Global Freight-Forwarding Companies

Table 4 shows that all LSQ factors are moderately important except from PDSQ to those 46-50 years old. For employees aged 41-45 years old, personnel contact quality, order handling quality, timeliness, and image are strongly important; and information quality and PDSQ are both important while social responsibility is moderately important. Then for those 36-40 years old, personnel contact quality, order handling quality, timeliness, and image are important; while information quality, PDSQ, and social responsibility were equally moderately important. Consequently, employees with ages 31-35 years old find personnel contact quality, information quality, timeliness, and social responsibility are moderately important; while the other LSQ such as order handling, PDSQ, and image are slightly important. Furthermore, those with 26-30 years old, personnel contact quality is important; and information quality, order handling quality, PDSQ, timeliness, and image are moderately important; while social responsibility is slightly important. Lastly, for 21-25 years old, all LSQ factors were equally important.

Table 4. Perception of the employees of global freight-forwarding companies according to age

Variables	PCQ	IQ	OHQ	PDSQ	Timeliness	Image	SR
46-50 years old	3	3	3	4	3	3	3
41-45 years old	5	4	5	4	5	5	3
36-40 years old	4	3	4	3	4	4	3
31-35 years old	3	3	2	2	3	2	3
26-30 years old	4	3	3	3	3	3	2
21-25 years old	4	4	4	4	4	4	4

Legend: PCQ – Personnel Contact Quality; IQ – Information Quality; OHQ – Order Handling Quality; PDSQ – Physical Distribution Service Quality; SR – Social Responsibility; 5 – Strongly Important; 4 – Important; 3 – Moderately Important; 2 – Slightly Important; 1 – Not Important

Table 5 shows that personnel contact quality, order handling quality, timeliness, and image are important; while information quality, PDSQ, and social responsibility are moderately important to male employees. In addition, all LSQ factors are equally slightly important to female employees.

Table 5. Perception of the employees of global freight-forwarding companies according to gender

Variables	PCQ	IQ	OHQ	PDSQ	Timeliness	Image	SR
Male	4	3	4	3	4	4	3
Female	2	2	2	2	2	2	2

Legend: PCQ – Personnel Contact Quality; IQ – Information Quality; OHQ – Order Handling Quality; PDSQ – Physical Distribution Service Quality; SR – Social Responsibility; 5 – Strongly Important; 4 – Important; 3 – Moderately Important; 2 – Slightly Important; 1 – Not Important

Table 6 shows perception of employees in terms of level of importance according to job level. Personnel contact quality, order handling quality, PDSQ, timeliness, and image are important to top management followed by information quality as moderately important and social responsibility as slightly important. For the middle management, all LSQ factors are slightly important. Then, for supervisory level,

all LSQ factors are moderately important; lastly, the rank and file, only personnel contact quality is important, and the others are all moderately important.

Table 6. Perception of the employees of global freight-forwarding companies according to job level

Variables	PCQ	IQ	OHQ	PDSQ	Timeliness	Image	SR
Top Management	4	3	4	4	4	4	2
Middle Management	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Supervisory	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Rank and File	4	3	3	3	3	3	3

Legend: PCQ – Personnel Contact Quality; IQ – Information Quality; OHQ – Order Handling Quality; PDSQ – Physical Distribution Service Quality; SR – Social Responsibility; 5 – Strongly Important; 4 – Important; 3 – Moderately Important; 2 – Slightly Important; 1 – Not Important

Logistics Service Quality Factors

Personnel Contact Quality

Personnel contact quality is a logistics service quality factor that refers to logistics service staff's attitude, behavior, and competence in handling customers' requirements and needs. As can be gleaned from the table, "Knowledge / understanding of customers' needs and requirements" obtained the highest mean of 4.97 as perceived by the respondents and verbally interpreted as strongly important. Staff's attitude and behavior in meeting customers' satisfaction" and "Responsiveness to customers' needs and requirements" both got the lowest mean of 4.64 and verbally interpreted as strongly important. The findings implied that the three (3) factors of personnel contact quality reflect on how the customers were highly satisfied with the abovementioned factors.

On the other hand, in the assessment of the employees of the global freight-forwarding companies, "Staff's attitude and behavior in meeting customers' satisfaction" obtained the highest mean of 4.74 as perceived by them and verbally interpreted as strongly important. It is followed by "Responsiveness to customers' needs and requirements" and "Knowledge / understanding of customers' needs and requirements" both with means of 4.70 verbally interpreted as strongly important. "Staff's competence" got the lowest mean of 4.32 and verbally interpreted as important. The findings implied that the four (4) factors of personnel contact quality reflect on how the employees of the global freight-forwarding companies highly prioritized the abovementioned factors.

Table 7. Personnel contact quality factors of the global freight-forwarding companies

Personnel Contact Quality	Customer	Interpretation	Employee	Interpretation
Staff's attitude and behavior in meeting customers' satisfaction	4.64	Strongly Important	4.74	Strongly Important
Responsiveness to customers' needs and requirements	4.64	Strongly Important	4.70	Strongly Important
Knowledge / understanding of customers' needs and requirements	4.97	Strongly Important	4.70	Strongly Important
Staff's competence			4.32	Important
Average Weighted Mean	4.75	Strongly Important	4.62	Strongly Important

Legend: 4.50-5.00 – Strongly Important; 3.50-4.49 – Important; 2.50-3.49 – Moderately Important; 1.50-2.49 – Slightly Important; 1.00-1.49 – Not Important

Information Quality

Information quality is a logistics service quality factor that refers to the reliability of information given by the logistics service provider. Among the five (5) factors under information quality in the survey questionnaire, the following were the ranking of the variables in terms of customers: information quality

aspect which state that, “Shipment tracing capability” yielded the highest weighted mean (4.71) and verbally interpreted as strongly important. Secondly, “Reliability of order information” yielded a weighted mean of 4.68 and verbally interpreted as strongly important. “Application of information technology (IT) and electronic data interchange (EDI) in customer service” got the lowest mean of 4.38 and verbally interpreted as important. The findings implied that the five (5) factors of information quality reflect on how the customers were highly satisfied with the abovementioned factors.

On the other hand, in terms of employees, the following were the ranking of the variables: information quality aspect which state that, “Shipment tracing capability” yielded the highest weighted mean (4.71) and verbally interpreted as strongly important. Secondly, “Reliability of order information” yielded a weighted mean of 4.62 and verbally interpreted as strongly important. “Availability of order information” got the lowest mean of 4.24 and verbally interpreted as important. The findings implied that the five (5) factors of information quality reflect on how the employees of the global freight-forwarding companies highly prioritized the abovementioned factors.

Table 8. Information quality factors of the global freight-forwarding companies

Information Quality	Customer	Interpretation	Employee	Interpretation
Reliability of order information	4.68	Strongly Important	4.62	Strongly Important
Introduction of IT innovation in customer service	4.60	Strongly Important	4.34	Important
Application of IT & electronic data interchange (EDI) in customer service	4.38	Important	4.34	Important
Availability of order information	4.67	Strongly Important	4.24	Important
Shipment tracing capability	4.71	Strongly Important	4.71	Strongly Important
Average Weighted Mean	4.61	Strongly Important	4.45	Strongly Important

Legend: 4.50-5.00 – Strongly Important; 3.50-4.49 – Important; 2.50-3.49 – Moderately Important; 1.50-2.49 – Slightly Important; 1.00-1.49 – Not Important

Order Handling Quality

Order handling quality is a logistics service quality factor that refers to the process of handling orders in terms of accuracy by the logistics service providers. Among the five (5) factors under order handling quality in the survey questionnaire, the following were the ranking of the variables in terms of customers: order handling quality aspect which state that, “Order accuracy (meeting customers’ requirements)” yielded the highest weighted mean (4.75) and verbally interpreted as strongly important. Secondly, “Consistency in order handling process” yielded a weighted mean of 4.68 and verbally interpreted as strongly important. “Consistency in order handling process” got the lowest mean of 4.52 and verbally interpreted as strongly important. The findings implied that the five (5) factors of order handling quality reflect on how the customers were highly satisfied with the abovementioned factors.

On the other hand, in terms of employees, the following were the ranking of the variables: order handling quality aspect which state that, “Order accuracy (meeting customers’ requirements)” yielded the highest weighted mean (4.76) and verbally interpreted as strongly important. Secondly, “Consistency in order handling process” yielded a weighted mean of 4.71 and verbally interpreted as strongly important. “Total order cycle time” got the lowest mean of 4.24 and verbally interpreted as strongly important. The findings implied that the five (5) factors of order handling quality reflect on how the employees of the global freight-forwarding companies highly prioritized the abovementioned factors.

Table 9. Order handling factors of the global freight-forwarding companies

Order Handling Quality	Customer	Interpretation	Employee	Interpretation
Order accuracy (meeting customers' requirements)	4.75	Strongly Important	4.76	Strongly Important
Order condition (free of damage, fault or loss)	4.68	Strongly Important	4.63	Strongly Important
Order discrepancy handling	4.66	Strongly Important	4.64	Strongly Important
Total order cycle time	4.54	Strongly Important	4.61	Strongly Important
Consistency in order handling process	4.52	Strongly Important	4.71	Strongly Important
Average Weighted Mean	4.66	Strongly Important	4.61	Strongly Important

Legend: 4.50-5.00 – Strongly Important; 3.50-4.49 – Important; 2.50-3.49 – Moderately Important; 1.50-2.49 – Slightly Important; 1.00-1.49 – Not Important

Physical Distribution Service Quality (PDSQ)

Physical Distribution Service Quality (PDSQ) is a logistics service quality factor that refers to conditions to meet customers' requirements of the logistics service providers. Among the five (5) factors under PDSQ in the survey questionnaire, the following were the ranking of the variables in terms of customers: PDSQ aspects which state that, "Consistence of service performance" and "Safety and security in delivery (intact and without loss or damage)" both yielded the highest weighted mean (4.68) and verbally interpreted as strongly important. Secondly, "Reliability of documentation (error-free)" yielded a weighted mean of 4.63. and verbally interpreted as strongly important. "Condition and availability of equipment and facilities" got the lowest mean of 4.58 and verbally interpreted as strongly important. The findings implied that the five (5) factors of Physical Distribution Service Quality (PDSQ) reflect on how the customers were highly satisfied with the abovementioned factors.

On the other hand, in terms of employees, the following were the ranking of the variables: PDSQ aspect which state that, "Safety and security in delivery (intact and without loss or damage)" yielded the highest weighted mean (4.73) and verbally interpreted as strongly important. Secondly, "Consistence of service performance" yielded a weighted mean of 4.64 and verbally interpreted as strongly important. "Reliability of documentation (error-free)" got the lowest mean of 4.45 and verbally interpreted as strongly important. The findings implied that the five (5) factors of Physical Distribution Service Quality (PDSQ) reflect on how the employees of the global freight-forwarding companies highly prioritized the above-mentioned factors.

Table 10. Physical Distribution Service Quality (PDSQ) factors of the global freight-forwarding companies

Physical Distribution Service Quality (PDSQ)	Customer	Interpretation	Employee	Interpretation
Condition and availability of equipment and facilities	4.58	Strongly Important	4.58	Strongly Important
Reliability, regularity, flexibility and availability of service (place and time utility)	4.62	Strongly Important	4.63	Strongly Important
Consistence of service performance	4.68	Strongly Important	4.64	Strongly Important
Safety and security in delivery (intact and without loss or damage)	4.68	Strongly Important	4.73	Strongly Important
Reliability of documentation (error-free)	4.63	Strongly Important	4.45	Strongly Important
Average Weighted Mean	4.64	Strongly Important	4.61	Strongly Important

Legend: 4.50-5.00 – Strongly Important; 3.50-4.49 – Important; 2.50-3.49 – Moderately Important; 1.50-2.49 – Slightly Important; 1.00-1.49 – Not Important

Timeliness

Timeliness is a logistics service quality factor that refers to the timely pick-up, delivery, and transportation by the service logistics providers. Among the two (2) factors under timeliness in the survey questionnaire, the following were the ranking of the variables in terms of customers: timeliness aspect which state that, "Timeliness of shipment pick-up and delivery" yielded the highest weighted mean (4.75)

and verbally interpreted as strongly important while “Transportation time” got the lowest mean of 4.64 and verbally interpreted as strongly important. The findings implied that the two (2) factors of timeliness reflect on how the customers are highly satisfied with the abovementioned factors.

On the other hand, in terms of employees, “Timeliness of shipment pick-up and delivery” yielded the highest weighted mean (4.77) and verbally interpreted as strongly important while “Transportation time” got the lowest mean of 4.58 and verbally interpreted as strongly important. The findings implied that the two (2) factors of timeliness reflect on how the employees of the global freight-forwarding companies highly prioritized the abovementioned factors.

Table 11. Timeliness factors of the global freight-forwarding companies

Timeliness	Customer	Interpretation	Employee	Interpretation
Timeliness of shipment pick-up and delivery	4.75	Strongly Important	4.77	Strongly Important
Transportation time	4.64	Strongly Important	4.58	Strongly Important
Average Weighted Mean	4.70	Strongly Important	4.68	Strongly Important

Legend: 4.50-5.00 – Strongly Important; 3.50-4.49 – Important; 2.50-3.49 – Moderately Important; 1.50-2.49 – Slightly Important; 1.00-1.49 – Not Important

Image

Image is a logistics service quality factor that refers to the logistics service provider's record and reputation in satisfying customers. Among the five (5) factors under Image in the survey questionnaire, the following were the ranking of the variables in terms of customers: Image aspect which state that, “Company’s record of professionalism and consistency in satisfying customers” yielded the highest weighted mean (4.72) and verbally interpreted as strongly important. Secondly, “Company’s reputation for matching words with action” yielded a weighted mean of 4.68 and verbally interpreted as strongly important. “Company’s ethical image” got the lowest mean of 4.55 and verbally interpreted as strongly important. The findings implied that the five (5) factors of image reflect on how the customers are highly satisfied with the abovementioned factors.

On the other hand, in terms of employees, the following were the ranking of the variables: Image aspect which state that, “Handling customer feedbacks (customers’ claim, complaints and returns)” yielded the highest weighted mean (4.66) and verbally interpreted as strongly important. Secondly, “Company’s reputation for reliability in the market” yielded a weighted mean of 4.65 and verbally interpreted as strongly important. “Company’s ethical image” got the lowest mean of 4.51 and verbally interpreted as strongly important. The findings implied that the five (5) factors of image reflect on how the employees of the global freight-forwarding companies highly prioritized the abovementioned factors.

Table 12. Image factors of the global freight-forwarding companies

Image	Customer	Interpretation	Employee	Interpretation
Handling customer feedbacks (customers’ claim, complaints and returns)	4.63	Strongly Important	4.66	Strongly Important
Company’s reputation for reliability in the market	4.66	Strongly Important	4.65	Strongly Important
Company’s record of professionalism and consistency in satisfying customers	4.72	Strongly Important	4.64	Strongly Important
Company’s reputation for matching words with action	4.68	Strongly Important	4.61	Strongly Important
Company’s ethical image	4.55	Strongly Important	4.51	Strongly Important
Average Weighted Mean	4.65	Strongly Important	4.61	Strongly Important

Legend: 4.50-5.00 – Strongly Important; 3.50-4.49 – Important; 2.50-3.49 – Moderately Important; 1.50-2.49 – Slightly Important; 1.00-1.49 – Not Important

Social Responsibility

Social responsibility is a logistics service quality factor that refers to logistics service provider's vision towards community responsibility. Among the four (4) factors under social responsibility in the survey questionnaire, the following were the ranking of the variables: social responsibility aspect which state that, "Performance statement and vision towards community responsibility" yielded the highest weighted mean (4.95) and verbally interpreted as strongly important. Secondly, "Environmentally safe operations" yielded a weighted mean of 4.59 and verbally interpreted as strongly important. "Record of engagement in community activities" got the lowest mean of 4.10 and verbally interpreted as strongly important. The findings implied that the four (4) factors of social responsibility reflect on how the customers were highly satisfied with the abovementioned factors.

On the other hand, in terms of employees, the following were the ranking of the variables: social responsibility aspect which state that, "Socially responsible behavior and concerns for human safety" and "Environmentally safe operations" both yielded the highest weighted mean (4.58) and verbally interpreted as strongly important. Secondly, "Performance statement and vision towards community responsibility" yielded a weighted mean of 4.52 and verbally interpreted as strongly important. "Record of engagement in community activities" got the lowest mean of 4.32 and verbally interpreted as strongly important. The findings implied that the four (4) factors of social responsibility reflect on how the employees of the global freight-forwarding companies highly prioritized the abovementioned factors.

Table 13. Social responsibility factors of the global freight-forwarding companies

Image	Customer	Interpretation	Employee	Interpretation
Socially responsible behavior and concerns for human safety	4.58	Strongly Important	4.58	Strongly Important
Environmentally safe operations	4.59	Strongly Important	4.58	Strongly Important
Record of engagement in community activities	4.10	Important	4.32	Important
Performance statement and vision towards community responsibility	4.95	Strongly Important	4.52	Strongly Important
Average Weighted Mean	4.56	Strongly Important	4.50	Strongly Important

Legend: 4.50-5.00 – Strongly Important; 3.50-4.49 – Important; 2.50-3.49 – Moderately Important; 1.50-2.49 – Slightly Important; 1.00-1.49 – Not Important

Statistical difference among each logistics service quality factor that affects perceived service quality

Customers

Business Type. Table 14 presents the summary of ANOVA showing the significant difference in the assessment of seven (7) factors of logistics service quality as rated by the respondents. Given the computed F value (0.80) which is lesser than the F critical value (9.488) at 5% level of significance, there is no significant difference on seven (7) factors of logistics service quality when respondents are grouped according to business type.

Table 14. Analysis of variance showing the significant difference on seven (7) factors of logistics service quality when respondents are grouped according to business type

Source of Variation	Df	SS	MS	Computed F Value	Critical F value ($\alpha=5\%$)	Interpretation	Decision
Between Groups	4	2.091	1.44	0.80	9.448	Not Significant	Retain the Ho
Within Groups	105	208.04	1.80				

Legend: Ho – Null Hypothesis; Df – Degree of Freedom; SS – Sum of Squares; MS – Mean Squares

Job Level. Table 15 presents the summary of ANOVA showing the significant difference in the assessment of seven (7) factors of logistics service quality as rated by the respondents. Given the computed F value (0.91) which is lesser than the F critical value (3.841) at 5% level of significance, there is no

significant difference on seven (7) factors of logistics service quality when respondents are grouped according to job level. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the assessment on seven (7) factors of logistics service quality when respondents are grouped according to job level.

Table 15. Analysis of variance showing the significant difference on seven (7) factors of logistics service quality when respondents are grouped according to job level of customers

Source of Variation	Df	SS	MS	Computed F Value	Critical F value ($\alpha=5\%$)	Interpretation	Decision
Between Groups	1	3.039	1.74	0.91	5.991	Not Significant	Retain the
Within Groups	104	241.68	1.91				Ho

Legend: Ho – Null Hypothesis; Df – Degree of Freedom; SS – Sum of Squares; MS – Mean Squares

Length of Service. Table 16 presents the summary of ANOVA showing the significant difference in the assessment of seven (7) factors of logistics service quality as rated by the respondents. Given the computed F value (0.91) which is lesser than the F critical value (5.991) at 5% level of significance, there is no significant difference on seven (7) factors of logistics service quality when respondents are grouped according to length of service. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the assessment on seven (7) factors of logistics service quality when respondents are grouped according to length of service.

Table 16. Analysis of variance showing the significant difference on seven (7) factors of logistics service quality when respondents are grouped according to length of service

Source of Variation	Df	SS	MS	Computed F Value	Critical F value ($\alpha=5\%$)	Interpretation	Decision
Between Groups	2	3.039	1.74	0.91	5.991	Not Significant	Retain the
Within Groups	104	211.68	1.91				Ho

Legend: Ho – Null Hypothesis; Df – Degree of Freedom; SS – Sum of Squares; MS – Mean Squares

Employees of the Global Freight-Forwarding Companies

Age. Table 17 presents the summary of ANOVA showing the significant difference in the assessment of seven (7) factors of logistics service quality as rated by the respondents. Given the computed F value (0.80) which is lesser than the F critical value (11.070) at 5% level of significance, there is no significant difference on seven (7) factors of logistics service quality when respondents are grouped according to age.

Table 17. Analysis of variance showing the significant difference on seven (7) factors of logistics service quality when respondents are grouped according to age

Source of Variation	Df	SS	MS	Computed F Value	Critical F value ($\alpha=5\%$)	Interpretation	Decision
Between Groups	5	2.091	1.44	0.80	11.070	Not Significant	Retain the
Within Groups	147	328.04	1.80				Ho

Legend: Ho – Null Hypothesis; Df – Degree of Freedom; SS – Sum of Squares; MS – Mean Squares

Gender. Table 18 presents the summary of ANOVA showing the significant difference in the assessment of seven (7) factors of logistics service quality as rated by the respondents. Given the computed F value (0.74) which is lesser than the F critical value (3.841) at 5% level of significance, there is no significant difference on seven (7) factors of logistics service quality when respondents are grouped according to gender.

Table 18. Analysis of variance showing the significant difference on seven (7) factors of logistics service quality when respondents are grouped according to gender

Source of Variation	Df	SS	MS	Computed F Value	Critical F value ($\alpha=5\%$)	Interpretation	Decision
Between Groups	1	2.196	1.40	0.74	3.841	Not Significant	Retain the Ho
Within Groups	147	337.60	1.92				

Legend: Ho – Null Hypothesis; Df – Degree of Freedom; SS – Sum of Squares; MS – Mean Squares

Job Level. Table 19 presents the summary of ANOVA showing the significant difference in the assessment of seven (7) factors of logistics service quality as rated by the respondents. Given the computed F value (0.74) which is lesser than the F critical value (7.815) at 5% level of significance, there is no significant difference on seven (7) factors of logistics service quality when respondents are grouped according to job level.

Table 19. Analysis of variance showing the significant difference on seven (7) factors of logistics service quality when respondents are grouped according to job level of employees

Source of Variation	Df	SS	MS	Computed F Value	Critical F value ($\alpha=5\%$)	Interpretation	Decision
Between Groups	4	2.196	1.40	0.74	7.815	Not Significant	Retain the Ho
Within Groups	147	347.60	1.92				

Legend: Ho – Null Hypothesis; Df – Degree of Freedom; SS – Sum of Squares; MS – Mean Squares

The transportation of commodities is "the spirit" of trade, hence freight forwarding businesses play a crucial role in advancing export-import commerce in the Philippines. In the freight forwarding market, where both domestic and international enterprises compete fiercely, organizations seeking to survive must exhibit exceptional performance, particularly during the pandemic.

A nation's economic activities are supported by the freight forwarding industry, particularly in the export and import sectors, given its status in Parañaque City. For freight forwarding companies, the growth of manufacturing, trading, retail, and other businesses presents huge possibilities for business. The freight forwarding industry in Parañaque is currently facing significant transformation, which, like any development, carries both opportunity and risk. Customization in manufacturing is growing, which is wonderful for consumers but challenging for the logistics sector. As a result, businesses now utilize technology to its fullest and most intelligent potential, whether it is for automation, data analytics, or the "Physical Internet."

In this case, it can be accomplished by investing in differentials or competitive advantage to increase the logistics service quality in the freight forwarding business in Parañaque. An advantage that a company has over its competitors is known as a competitive advantage. As a result, a company can outperform its competitors and generate value for both it and its stockholders. A competitive advantage ought to be hard to replicate, if not impossible. It is not seen as a competitive advantage if it is simple to duplicate or mimic.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In every industry, competition is getting stronger day by day especially in the freight forwarding and logistics industry. Therefore, to maintain the competitive advantage of freight forwarding and logistics service providers they should be mindful of the perceived service quality they offer their customers. Hence, service quality must meet the customers' expectations and satisfaction by assessing logistics service quality factors and improving them if necessary.

Age, gender, and job level of the employees of global freight-forwarding companies were not statistically significant on the seven (7) factors of logistics service quality. The findings implied that among the seven (7) factors of logistics service quality, it reflects that information quality was the least priority among the factors as perceived by the employees of global freight-forwarding companies. Commonly, they focused on timeliness aspect. On the other hand, the organization is more focused on the personnel contact quality aspect. The freight forwarding market is very competitive, involving both domestic and foreign enterprises that wish to survive must maintain a certain level of quality. Consumer demand has remained stronger throughout the pandemic, with e-commerce providing a crucial sale outlet. A nation's economy is supported in part by the freight forwarding industry, particularly in the export and import sectors. Improved logistics service quality in freight forwarding business in Parañaque can be achieved by investing to competitive advantage, specifically to personnel contact quality as it involves good customer service.

The researcher suggested a proposal and dialogue with the management to strategize the improvement of logistics service quality, especially having the new normal because of the pandemic. This is to establish and maintain effective partnerships with all resource partners, update them, and actively participate in each other's activities to have a sound logistics service quality. Further study on the logistics service quality relative to budget is necessary to determine its importance among freight forwarding and logistics service providers to increase their service quality to meet and exceed their expectations. Further study on the logistics service quality is necessary to determine other underlying factors. Seminars on the seven factors of Logistics Service Quality (LSQ), namely: 1) Personnel Contact Quality; 2) Information Quality; 3) Order Handling Quality; 4) Physical Distribution Service Quality (PDSQ); 5) Timeliness; 6) Image; and 7) Social Responsibility must be conducted to enhance the services in the attainment of higher customer satisfaction.

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